

CONTEMPORARY PERSPECTIVES ON PERIODONTITIS DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060056>

Annotation. Periodontitis remains one of the most prevalent chronic inflammatory diseases worldwide, affecting approximately 750 million people globally and representing a significant public health challenge in both developed and developing countries. This multifactorial disease continues to be a leading cause of tooth loss in adults and has shown increasing associations with various systemic conditions, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, and adverse pregnancy outcomes.

Key words: stomatology, periodontics, periodontium, periodontal diseases, pathology, etiology, pathogenesis, etiopathogenesis.

Introduction. Recent advances in molecular biology, immunology, and microbiome research have dramatically transformed our understanding of periodontal disease pathogenesis. The traditional linear model of periodontitis progression has evolved into a complex network of interactions between microbial communities, host immune responses, and environmental factors. Modern research has revealed that the disease's development extends far beyond the simplistic concept of bacterial accumulation and subsequent host response.

The emergence of new technologies, particularly in the fields of genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, has provided unprecedented insights into the intricate mechanisms underlying periodontal tissue destruction. These technological advances have enabled researchers to identify novel pathogenic pathways, potential therapeutic targets, and biomarkers for early disease detection. Furthermore, the recognition of periodontitis as a dysbiotic disease rather than a classical infectious disease has fundamentally changed our approach to understanding its etiology and progression.

The complex interplay between the oral microbiome and host immunity has emerged as a central theme in contemporary periodontal research. Recent studies have highlighted the role of keystone pathogens in disrupting homeostasis and initiating inflammatory cascades that lead to tissue destruction. This paradigm shift has important implications for both disease prevention and treatment strategies.

Environmental factors, including smoking, stress, and dietary habits, have been increasingly recognized as crucial modulators of periodontal disease progression. Additionally, genetic susceptibility factors and epigenetic modifications have been identified as important determinants of individual disease susceptibility and severity. Understanding these various contributing factors is essential for developing personalized therapeutic approaches and improving treatment outcomes.

The economic burden of periodontitis treatment, coupled with its impact on quality of life, underscores the importance of understanding disease mechanisms for developing more effective preventive and therapeutic strategies. Current estimates suggest that periodontal diseases account for a substantial portion of global healthcare expenditure, with direct treatment costs exceeding \$54 billion annually in developed countries alone.

The advent of new diagnostic tools and therapeutic modalities has opened new avenues for periodontal disease management. However, optimal utilization of these advances requires a thorough understanding of the underlying disease mechanisms. This comprehensive review aims to synthesize current knowledge about periodontitis pathogenesis, incorporating recent discoveries in host-microbe interactions, inflammatory mediators, and tissue healing responses.

Understanding the contemporary perspectives on periodontitis development and progression is crucial not only for advancing our scientific knowledge but also for developing more effective therapeutic strategies. This review will examine the latest evidence regarding the complex interactions between microbial communities, host responses, and environmental factors that contribute to periodontal disease initiation and progression, with particular emphasis on recent technological advances that have enhanced our understanding of these processes.

Conclusions: The landscape of periodontal research has undergone remarkable transformation in recent decades, revolutionizing our understanding of periodontitis pathogenesis and progression. This chronic inflammatory condition, affecting approximately 20-50% of the global population, has emerged as a complex disease entity with far-reaching implications beyond oral health. Modern research has established periodontitis as not merely a localized oral infection, but rather a systemic condition with significant implications for overall health and well-being.

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